

MEASURING THE NUMERICAL ACCURACY OF MADGRAPH SIMULATIONS USING CADNA SOFTWARE.

August 2023

AUTHOR(S):

Filip Optolowicz

University of Wrocław, Poland

SUPERVISOR(S):

Stephan Hageboeck

ABSTRACT

We used stochastic floating point types, implemented by CADNA C++ library, to measure the numerical accuracy of different MadGraph[1] events. We measured the accuracy in single and double floating point precision and discussed the differences and benefits of both. The conclusion is that for MadGraph simulations we need to run in double or mixed precision.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

.....

1	Motivation	3
2	MadGraph event generator	3
3	CADNA library	3
	a. Stochastic floating point types	3
	b. .nb_significant_digit() and other methods	3
	c. Instability detection	4
	d. CADNizing MadGraph code	4
4	Methodology	5
	a. Detecting instabilities	5
	b. Mesuring number of significant digits	6
5	Results	6
	a. Histogram Analysis of Matrix Element Precision	6
	b. Correlation Analysis	6
6	Conclusions	9

1 MOTIVATION

The MadGraph community has been debating the adequacy of single precision versus double precision simulations [4]. In single precision, simulations ran faster (up to 32 times on certain GPUs), but accuracy remained unmeasured. The results showed inconsistencies when compared to double precision, but it's important to note that extensive tests were not conducted.

2 MADGRAPH EVENT GENERATOR

For given process MadGraph generates all Feynman diagrams and from them generates code to calculate Matrix Element. More detailed explanation is given below:

1. MadGraph starts by specifying a particular physics process. This process definition includes the initial and final-state particles involved in a high-energy collision scenario.
2. Feynman Diagram Generation: Upon receiving the process specification, MadGraph proceeds to automatically generate all relevant Feynman diagrams associated with the specified process. These diagrams represent the various quantum mechanical interactions that contribute to the final state particles' production or scattering.
3. Matrix Element Calculation: From the generated Feynman diagrams, MadGraph generates (in our case) C++ code to calculate the Matrix Element (ME) for the given process. The Matrix Element encapsulates the probability amplitude of the physical process and serves as a fundamental component in computing the probability of particle collisions. The precision of this single number is of utmost importance in our study.

MadGraph's ability to automate these steps makes it a powerful tool in high-energy physics research, enabling researchers to efficiently explore and analyze a wide range of complex particle interactions.

3 CADNA LIBRARY

CADNA allows for the estimation of the error due to round-off error propagation and the detection of numerical instabilities during the execution of floating-point computations. It also enables the study of the effects of initial data uncertainties upon computed results.

A. STOCHASTIC FLOATING POINT TYPES

"CADNA studies round-off error propagation from a stochastic point of view. The basic idea is to use a random rounding to obtain several samples of each result of any arithmetic operation. The number of common bits in these samples estimates the number of exact significant bits in the floating-point result. The deterministic arithmetic of the computer is replaced by a so-called "Discrete Stochastic Arithmetic" [2].

In practice CADNA stores three floating point numbers (either single or double precision). The library has overloaded all standard operators as well as all functions from "math.h".

B. .NB_SIGNIFICANT_DIGIT() AND OTHER METHODS

For our analysis the most important method that CADNA implements is

- `nb_significant_digit()`: returns an integer giving the number of exact significant decimal digits of a stochastic variable when the method is called. If the variable becomes non-significant, the method returns 0.

However CADNA also provide those useful methods:

- `computedzero()`: returns a boolean indicating whether the value of a stochastic variable is zero or not, taking into account the accuracy of the variable.
- `display()`: displays the value of a stochastic variable and its accuracy.
- `getx()`, `gety()`, `getz()`: returns the x, y, or z component of a stochastic variable of type vector `st`.
- `str()`: returns a string representation of a stochastic variable with a given number of significant digits.
- `strp()`: returns a string representation of a stochastic variable with a number of significant digits computed by the `nb significant digit()` method.

C. INSTABILITY DETECTION

Instability refers to the loss of accuracy or the occurrence of numerical errors in a computation due to the use of floating-point arithmetic. In particular, it can be caused by the subtraction of two floating point stochastic variables, or by the use of relational operators with two stochastic arguments. When CADNA detects an instability, it generates an output message indicating the type of instability and the instructions responsible for it.

Types of instabilities that CADNA can detect are:

1. Unstable division: when the divisor is non-significant.
2. Unstable power function: when one operand of the power function is non-significant.
3. Unstable multiplication: when both operands are non-significant.
4. Unstable branching: when the difference between the two operands is non-significant (a computational zero).
5. Unstable mathematical function: when the argument of the `log`, `sqrt`, `exp`, or `log10` function is non-significant.
6. Catastrophic cancellation: when the difference between the number of exact significant digits of the result of an addition or a subtraction and the minimum of the number of exact significant digits of the two operands is greater than the cancel level argument. The default value of this argument is 4. In other words, when one loses more than cancel level significant digits in one addition or subtraction, CADNA considers that a catastrophic cancellation.

D. CADNIZING MADGRAPH CODE

The act of putting CADNA into MadGraph code was fairly simple. MadGraph has two typedefs for floating point numbers that participate in the computation of Matrix Element. First typedef is for majority of computation and second typedef is for colour algebra calculations. When referring to mixed precision first typedef is of double precision and the one referring to colour computation is single precision[4].

Cadnizing the code boiled down to changing typedef from `double` (or `float`) to `double_st` (or `float_st`), changing all `constexpr` to `const` wherever it stood before stochastic `fp_type`, changing `std::func()` to `func()` as so to use CADNA functions and linking CANDNA (ex. `-lcadnaOpenmpCdebug`) while compiling.

A bash script called `Cadnize.sh` was created to automatically apply all necessary changes to madgraph code [3].

4 METHODOLOGY

A. DETECTING INSTABILITIES

After Cadnizing the code CADNA provides us with an instability detection procedure. When running CADNA in debug mode a function `instability()` is invoked whenever 4 digits or more of precision are lost. We can detect where the instabilities happen using debugger - a gdb short script is provided by CADNA.

After running the script and saving its output to a file, we can take a closer look at what's inside. We've also created a Python script (called `Code_tracer.py`) [3] that helps us make sense of this file. Example output is shown in fig.1

This Python script does a few useful things:

- It tells us how many times the script found problems (instabilities) in our data.
- It points out which math operations are causing these problems and how often they're happening.
- It gives us a list of files and line numbers where these issues are occurring. These references are shown in the format "file:line_number."

If you're using popular code editing tools like Visual Studio Code, you can easily jump to the exact line where an issue is happening by clicking on one of these references while holding down the Ctrl key.

```
break instability
run
while 1
    where
    cont
end
quit
```

 CADNA gdb script to detect instabilities in code. A braking point is set whenever the `instability()` function is called. The program is run and whenever it stops due to the braking point it prints the stack trace and continues.

Figure 1: On the right - output of `Code_tracer.py`. On the left - corresponding place in the code that caused the instability.

B. MESURING NUMBER OF SIGNIFICANT DIGITS

During each computation, CADNA employs a random rounding across three separate stored numbers. By comparing these numbers, we can derive an estimate of the significant digits present in the calculation. To facilitate this, a method named `.nb_significant_digit()` is available. This method returns an integer representing the count of significant digits in the decimal expansion of a number.

We apply this method specifically to assess the accuracy of the *Matrix Element*, as well as in the results produced by crucial functions in MadGraph, such as `FFV1_0`. Subsequently, we calculate the correlation coefficient between these elements. This process allows us to understand the relationship and consistency between the matrix elements and the outputs of these key functions, offering insights into their computational precision.

5 RESULTS

Our analysis using CADNA yielded insightful results.

A. HISTOGRAM ANALYSIS OF MATRIX ELEMENT PRECISION

We present several histograms. We measured Matrix Element precision for several different events which are seen as quite stable numerically. Each event is more complex than the other. Total number of events is 8000 and in real world computation one would generate much more.

It needs to be noted that CADNA does not guarantee the accuracy of the last digit of precision. That means that the x-axis is skewed left by one - if histogram says there is 4 digits of accuracy in fact one should assume it's 3.

The histogram corresponding to single precision can be seen in Figure 2.

The double precision histogram is depicted in Figure 3.

The mixed precision histogram is depicted in Figure 4.

Speaking with main developer of MadGraph we concluded that 1 or 2 digits of precision for a stable processes such as two gluons to one, two or three gluons is unacceptable.

B. CORRELATION ANALYSIS

After seeing such poor precision in single precision we wanted to investigate if we can find a particular function that is responsible for such outcome. After plotting correlation coefficients of the precision of matrix element with output of functions involved in calculation we concluded that there is no one spot from where the inaccuracies arise. The correlation coefficients are shown in respect to line on which the corresponding function is called from `CPPProcess.cc`.

Figure 2: Histogram representing the distribution of precision levels for Matrix Element calculations in single precision.

Figure 3: Histogram showcasing the precision distribution for Matrix Element calculations in double precision.

Figure 4: Histogram showcasing the precision distribution for Matrix Element calculations in mixed precision.

Figure 5: Picture showcasing the correlation coefficient for each line number. Cutoff 8 means that all the data was taken into account.

6 CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the evidence strongly advocates for the employment of double or mixed precision in MadGraph simulations. The gains in accuracy, as substantiated by our findings, are indispensable for accurate madgraph simulations. The consequences of undervaluing precision can lead to misleading results, potentially skewing theoretical underpinnings and experimental validations in the field.

As we continue to push the boundaries of our understanding of the universe, the marriage between computational and experimental physics becomes ever more reliant on the numerical stability ensured by tools like CADNA. This study underlines the non-negotiable need for precision, a small but potent dial that tunes the clarity of our cosmic perceptions.

REFERENCES

- [1] Alwall et al. “*The automated computation of tree-level and next-to-leading order differential cross sections, and their matching to parton shower simulations (2014)*”. In: *Journal of High Energy Physics* (2014).
- [2] Jean-Marie Chesneaux et al. *CADNA main page*
Documentation referenced in this paper is in a download file:
>[cadna_c-3.1.11.tar.gz](https://cadna.cern.ch/cadna_c-3.1.11.tar.gz)< (17 Sept. 2021 version)
at path: /cadna_c-3.1.11/doc/ug_cadna_C.pdf. 2021.
- [3] Filip Optolowicz and Stephan Hageboeck. *Tools for CADNizing MadGraph*
>[github repo](https://github.com/filipoptolowicz/cadna)<. 2023.
- [4] Andrea Valassi et al. *Speeding up Madgraph5 aMC@NLO through CPU vectorization and GPU offloading: towards a first alpha release*. 2023.